

WRF Model Methods in Detail

Three domains were created and according to “WRF Users’ Guide” (n.d.), the nested domains must be inside of the parent domain. So domains 2 and 3 are inside of domain 1. However, the nested domains must not be bordering and be at least 10 grid point away from the lateral boundaries of the parent domain. This ensures that the boundary effects are reduced. So, the meteorological data which is updated every six hours on the outer boundary of domain 1, has little effect when assessing WRF’s performance further inside of the domains. Since WRF works with nesting domains, the resolution can only decrease by a factor of three or five. The workflow of WRF can be divided into three distinct parts: pre-processing, processing and post-processing. This is described and summarized in the figure below.

First the pre-processing took place. Static geographical data is used as the input for geogrid, which together with the namelist.wps was used to select the correct domains, see figure 3.1. This was based on a trial-and-error approach, where the namelist.wps was iteratively adjusted and visualized until the domains aligned with the research requirements.

Next ungrib was performed. For this ERA5 reanalysis data was needed in GRIB format, this served as the initial and the boundary conditions. WRF used ERA5 data on single and on pressure level (Hersbach et al., 2023a, 2023b). The data was downloaded through the Copernicus website. For the single levels the following parameters were downloaded: 10m u-component of the wind, 10m v-component of the wind, 2m dewpoint temperature, 2m temperature, sea surface temperature, surface pressure, mean sea level pressure, skin temperature, snow depth, snow density, soil temperatures (on levels 1-4), volumetric soil water layer (on levels 1-4), land sea mask and sea-ice cover. This was done for latitude 89N to 60N and 50W to 50E from 12 UTC 2020-03-18 until 6 UTC 2020-03-21. Next, data was selected at 00, 06, 12 and 18 UTC, the boundary conditions were selected to be updated every six hours in WRF. The GRIB format was selected and the data was downloaded.

The second type of input data WRF needed was on pressure levels. The following parameters were selected: geopotential, temperature, u-component of wind, v-component of wind, specific humidity and relative humidity. This is done for all the available pressure levels. Again this was done for latitude 89N to 60N and 50W to 50E from 12 UTC 2020-03-18 until 6 UTC 2020-03-21, at times 00, 06, 12 and 18 UTC. Again the GRIB format was downloaded. The data was uploaded to the high performance computer (HPC) Anunna.

Once geogrid and ungrib were completed, the interim files were used as input for metgrid. Metgrid combined the geographical and meteorological data into files that were used for the realjob. The pre-processing had to be done only once to answer sub-question one. To answer the second sub-question the pre-processing had to be done per experimental run.

Once the pre-processing was completed, the processing could start. The namelist.input is an important part in the processing of WRF. The settings in this file had to match the namelist.wps from the pre-processing. Additionally, the namelist.input was where the physical parameterization schemes were selected. For the five different configurations the namelist.input had to be altered per run.

The interim files created by metgrid (part of pre-processing) were used as input for realjob. Realjob then created the input files which were used by the wrfjob, which was when WRF really ran. This completed the processing part. This process was repeated five times for sub-question one, since the parameterization schemes differ, resulting in five unique WRF outputs.

Once the processing was finished, the post-processing using Python was performed. Post-processing turned the WRF output from netcdf files into text files or spatial maps. These text files could then be used to compare to observations.

Summary of WRFs work flow.